

FUNCTIONS AND CLASSIFICATION OF LOBBYISM IN LEGAL RELATIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Olimjonov Sohibjon Olimjon ugli,

*Leading Adviser of the International Cooperation Department
of the Secretariat of the Central Election Commission
of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

ANNOTATION: *This thesis provides detailed information about lobbying, its types and components, as well as the origin and development of this phenomenon and its functions. In addition, the role of this phenomenon in the experience of foreign countries, in particular in the United States, Japan and the EU countries, is illustrated by examples of the consequences of legalizing activities in these countries, along with specific aspects of activity. In addition, information is provided on the contribution of the event to the economic and legal spheres.*

Keywords: *lobbyism, term, foreign experience, function, type, theory, scientists, foreign countries, consequences.*

ФУНКЦИИ И КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ЛОББИЗМА В ПРАВООТНОШЕНИЯХ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ

Олимжонов Соhibжон Олимжон углы,

*Ведущий консультант отдела Международного
сотрудничества Секретариата Центральной
избирательной комиссии Республики Узбекистан*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В данном тезисе представлена подробная информация о лоббизме, его видах и компонентах, а также о происхождении и развитии этого явления и его функциях. Кроме того, роль данного явления в опыте зарубежных стран, в частности в США, Японии и странах Евросоюза, иллюстрируется примерами последствий легализации деятельности в этих странах, наряду с конкретными аспектами деятельности. Кроме того, предоставляется информация о вкладе мероприятия в экономическую и правовую сферы.*

Ключевые слова: *лоббирование, термин, зарубежный опыт, функция, вид, теория, ученые, зарубежные страны, последствия.*

ХУҚУҚИЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ЛОББИЗМНИНГ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ ВА ТАСНИФИ: ҚИЁСИЙ ТАҲЛИЛ

Олимжонов Соҳибжон Олимжон ўғли,
*Ўзбекистон Республикаси Марказий сайлов комиссияси
Котибияти Халқаро ҳамкорлик бўлими етакчи маслаҳатчиси*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *Мазкур тезисда лоббизм, унинг турлари ва таркибий қисмлари, шунингдек, ушбу ҳодисанинг келиб чиқиши ва ривожланиши ҳамда унинг функциялари тўғрисида батафсил маълумот келтирилган. Қолаверса, ушбу ҳодисанинг хорижий мамлакатлар тажрибасида, хусусан, АҚШ, Япония ва Европа Иттифоқи мамлакатларида тутган ўрни, ушбу мамлакатларда фаолиятнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари билан биргаликда фаолиятнинг легаллаштириш оқибати мисоллар ёрдамида очиб берилган. Бундан ташқари, ҳодисанинг иқтисодий ва ҳуқуқий соҳаларига қўшадиган ҳиссалари тўғрисида маълумот баён этилган.*

Калит сўзлар: *лоббизм, атама, хорижий тажриба, функция, тури, назария, олимлар, хорижий давлатлар, оқибатлар.*

In science, the concept of the function of law has been studied quite thoroughly. In addition, this problem can hardly be classified as one of the most acute, debatable in the theory of state and law. Disputes mainly revolve around various types of functions of law, criteria for their classification, functions of individual elements of the system of law – spheres, institutions, norms. With regard to the concept of the function of law, scientists show rare unanimity: views differ only in the part concerning some components of this concept and their combination in the basic definition of the function of law. Sometimes appear discussions about the relationship between the functions of law and other legal categories, for example, the tasks of law. Such a scientific polemic does not violate the general point of view on the functions of law – even extreme views on this or that particular problem of functions fit into the framework of the fundamental provisions of the concept itself.

The function of law in its classical understanding is a unity of two aspects: a) the role (purpose) of law in society; b) the main directions of its impact on

social relation³⁷. A similar approach to the concept of the function of law, proposed by T.N. Radko³⁸, synthesizes, in essence, the views of scientists who reduce this category to one of the above components. Thus, some authors, when defining the functions of law, focus on their "role" aspect. According to Y.G. Tkachenko, the functions of law should be understood as the specific role (action) of law in the organization of social relations³⁹. V.D. Filimonov points out that "the functions of law are the social role that it plays in the organization (ordering) of public relations. relations, determined by the direction and method of their legal regulation"⁴⁰.

Activity in general, whatever kind it may be, performs a specific function. Naturally, we are primarily interested in those functions that have a socially significant, that is, legal nature.

The legal sphere of the life of society is a prism where all other spheres, its components, intersect. Therefore, it is easy to guess that it is here that the concentration of lobbying will be the highest and, accordingly, the most significant.

First function, lobbying groups act as mediators between citizens and the state. This mediation takes place primarily in the area of information exchange. Of course, expert knowledge plays an important role in the enactment of laws or in the interpretation of legislation by government officials in the course of its direct implementation. But the knowledge of citizens themselves, directly passed through the interest, concentrated in lobbying structures, sometimes turns out to be much more important both from the point of view of formal accuracy and from the point of view of the legitimacy of the decisions made. The latter is significant because it shows that lobbying, ideally, is not a "one-way street". Pressure groups seek benefits for themselves, but, in turn, provide favorable conditions for the perception by society and specific groups of the population of laws and administrative actions adopted and undertaken by the state.

Second function, lobbying serves of organizing a pluralism of public interests. It is a necessary institution of a pluralistic society. Naturally, each person and groups of persons, especially those united in organizations and unions, engaged in specific activities, in particular, economic, have their own specific interests. All people and their groups strive to defend their interests with the means available to them, taking into account social, economic and

³⁷ Radko T.N. Concept and types of functions of socialist law // Problems of the theory of state and law. Saratov, 2011. Issue. 2 / Ed. M. I. Baytilna and V. V. Borisov. P. 108;

³⁸ Abramov Andrey Ivanovich The concept of the function of law // Journal of Russian law. 2008. No. 2 (110).

³⁹ Tkachenko Y. G. Methodological questions of the theory of legal relations. M., 2010. P. 34.

⁴⁰ Filimonov V. D. Protective function of criminal law. SPb., 2013. P. 50.

legal norms. It is quite logical that interests, acting in a limited field, begin to collide, and legal methods and mechanisms are needed to compare interests and determine their priorities. Lobbying processes are always carried out by a small group of people, but the results of lobbying have significant consequences and in some cases affect large segments of the country's population, especially the economic side of its life.

The positive aspects of lobbyism are not only in the fact that someone, acting in their own interests, “is pushing a business necessary for society” (if this is not to the detriment of others, but in the general interests, for example, “what is beneficial for Ford”, then it is beneficial for America”). This is beneficial to society for a formal democratic reason, so to speak, because the comparison of group interests, opportunities and consequences of various kinds of actions, carried out within the framework of a democratic procedure and expressed in political decisions, forms a complex system of costs and balances of economic agents. If this is how lobbyism is understood, then it should not be rejected. It is more useful to understand the possible options for its use and to legitimize acceptable forms.

Third function, lobbyism, as it were, complements the constitutional system of democratic representation, allowing those groups that do not have such other opportunity to participate in the adoption and implementation of political decisions. Since the parliament is formed according to territorial districts and party lists, a huge number of the most diverse social groups, each with its own particular interest, cannot articulate it, its own interest, nominating their own deputies. At the same time, her interest can be both narrowly particular and of great public importance. Thus, through the system and practice of lobbying, interests that would otherwise remain unexpressed are expressed and represented on a national scale. In this sense, lobbying is in the spirit of democratic politics.

Of course, the way lobbyism appears according to this definition, that is, what it should be in its functions and political meaning, does not always correspond to the realities of its existence in specific political and national contexts. This is primarily because lobbyism, like other political institutions, is not constructed from scratch by political “technologists”, but grows out of real inter human and intergroup relations under the influence of the dominant political tradition and the characteristics of the historical moment. Therefore, it functions differently in different countries.

In one form or another, lobbyism actually exists in any developed society, but the degree of its development, civilization, intensity of use and productivity depend on the nature of the political regime, the structure of the political system, political culture, historical traditions and other features of each specific

country. The general normative indicator of the intensity and effectiveness of lobbying activity is the resolution of the political system, which is understood, first of all, the number and quality of access points available in it, using which interest groups can be involved in the decision-making process by public authorities.

However, not in all countries lobbyism is legalized and become an independent legal institution. For instance, rigid institutionalization of lobbyist groups exists in Austria, France, Netherlands and some other countries. The institute of lobbying in them acts as a socio-economic council performing an advisory and advisory function, and also has a decisive vote in the legislative process.

In 2012, the National Council in Austria passed the Law on Transparency of Lobbying and Lobbying activities, the Law on Political Parties, which toughens criminal norms against corruption, and the Law on Incompatibility and Transparency for deputies⁴¹.

Since 1 May 2018, France's new lobbying law is fully implemented. Part and parcel of recent legislation on transparency (Sapin II package), it was adopted on 9 December 2016, providing a regulatory framework for lobbying activities and establishing a mandatory national register ('le repertoire') for lobbyists. In a step-by-step process, first, the repertoire, in which all active interest representatives must sign up, was created on 1 July 2017. After registering by 1 January 2018, interest representatives were then under the obligation to report their lobbying activities in this repertoire by 30 April 2018. The repertoire, with just over 100 registrants to date, is overseen by the 'Haute Autorité pour la Transparence de la Vie Publique' (HATVP). In France, the cultural acceptance of lobbying as a profession has been slow, and the new law will make a huge difference in terms of making lobbying activities public, with a regulation closely following the Irish example. The Sapin II package aims for a general increase in public accountability and transparency of the decision-making processes. Some incremental steps in this direction had been taken previously, primarily with the establishment of the HATVP in January 2014 as an independent body to oversee the integrity and transparency of the national public institutions⁴².

With regard to lobbying, an access point is considered to be any element of the political system (a state body or its subdivision, a parliamentary faction, a party mechanism, elections of deputies or other officials, procedure, jurisdiction, authority, and so on) that has the qualities that make it capable in the

⁴¹ Available from: <https://option.news/ru/lobbying-in-oesterreich-geheime-einfluesterer/> (accessed on 11 May 2021).

⁴² See. Published by EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service Authors: Elisabeth Bauer and Marie Thiel with Irene Vlad Transparency Unit, Directorate-General for the Presidency PE 625.104 – July 2018.

aggregate with other elements or even independently play a significant or decisive, or even decisive role in the fate of the draft law or administrative act under consideration. The highlighted words contain the main characteristic, without which this or that element cannot claim to be an effective access point. An example to illustrate: most bills approved by the leading committees of the US Congresses, as a rule, successfully pass all subsequent procedures and become laws. Consequently, if a stakeholder group has been able to get such a committee to positively consider a bill or amendment it wants, it can really count on ultimate success. In this case, the committee was one but practically effective point of access for this interest group.

It follows from all that has been said that the more favorable the conditions for lobbying activity are the more such access points are in the political system. Their number directly depends on the anatomy of this system.

The more branched and more complex it is structured, the more it contains not only permanently existing, but also potentially possible access points, the variety of options for the interaction of its constituent elements, and under a certain set of circumstances, this or that option can give either a new permanent or a uniform access point.

The considered characteristics are most consistent with the political systems of developed countries of pluralistic democracy.

It is very important to note here that in those political systems where the executive branch plays a decisive role in the adoption and implementation of legislative acts, "corridor lobbying" is developing. This phenomenon was strongly developed in our country, especially during stagnant years. To date, it has naturally undergone some changes.

Its essence lies, first of all, in pushing the pleasing and slowing down or completely refusing to make an undesirable decision. To this end, it is most important to have and support "your" people in key positions. Moreover, in the apparatus hierarchy, official posts and the real degree of influence on decisions made often do not coincide. That is why the balance of power in key positions and the degree of their influence on the leadership, including those who are not even included in the official nomenclature, are so closely watched by the participants in the lobbying process.

The main methods of "corridor work" are that it is necessary to know all the subtleties of the functioning of the apparatus, the decision-making system and the psychological characteristics of this or that leader, the degree of influence on him by the immediate environment. For example, the easiest way to drown any decision is to send it for approval to at least five different ministries and departments, appointing the head department, which is clearly overloaded with work or does not have due weight. In exceptional cases,

methods of direct influence are used through the organization of companies in the media.

Moreover, in the conditions of today's Uzbekistan, the calculation is not based on the influence of public opinion, which no one has taken into account for a long time and is not afraid, but as a channel for bringing information to the head and creating in him the impression of the great social significance of the problem.

Also of great importance is the organization of field visits to regions and enterprises by the head, when during well-organized "shows" one can achieve significant results in solving certain problems.

In addition, when it comes the subjects of the right of legislative initiative in Uzbekistan, they are followings:

- The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- The Republic of Karakalpakstan, represented by its highest representative body of state power;
- deputies of the Legislative Chamber;
- The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- The Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- The Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- General Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Our understanding of lobbying would generally not be complete if we had not outlined, at least in general terms, exactly what goals are pursued by lobbying. There is no doubt that in each specific case, these may be the most diverse interests. It also depends on the sphere of public life where lobbying activities take place, and on the quality level of state structures, on the qualitative composition of the "pressure groups" themselves, and much, much more. But a number of the most general goals pursued by lobbyists can be distinguished. If we turn to Uzbek practice, then the analysis of the adopted presidential decrees and government resolutions, their orders and appointments can be a rather striking example of lobbyist groups (it is our personal opinion). First of all, it is noteworthy that, with the exception of the issues of awarding orders and titles (which are regularly produced, but without much advertising), the main interests of lobbying groups are concentrated around customs benefits, permission to privatize enterprises according to a special scheme and on the allocation of preferential credit and public investment.

Hopes for budget allocation of funds in the absence of money in the budget have recently become very illusory, therefore, at the door of the Ministry of Finance, a wave of walkers with papers signed at the highest level and

dissatisfied with the standard answer about the lack of money does not dry up. Note in parallel that budget lobbying is divided into sectoral and regional.

Therefore, the center of gravity of privileges is shifted to customs privileges, since their real size and expenditure are practically uncontrollable. Customs privileges in combination with the allocation of quotas and licenses for the export of strategic resources constitute today a very significant privilege, which is most often granted only by a presidential decree.

The allocation of direct public investments has lost its former attractiveness, mainly due to the complexity of registration and the weak chances of their real allocation due to the reduction in the budget revenues. Privatization issues, being the most confusing and uncertain, legally allow lobbyist groups to redistribute property in accordance with their own interests. Even within the framework of Presidential Decrees regulating privatization, there are many issues that can be resolved while remaining in the legislative field. This applies, first of all, to the determination of the value of objects, which very often causes surprise, the procedure for holding auctions, determining the part of the property that remains at the disposal of the state, and so on.

Speaking of status privileges, one can mention the creation of free economic zones.

But the variant of lobbying, as described above, is the practice of pressure from the bottom to up, from the self-organizing interests of certain groups of the population on state bodies in order to obtain certain advantages, benefits, privileges for these groups. Moreover, the state sovereignly controls the distribution of resources, statuses, economic and social benefits. Interest groups try to influence the state, but, ultimately, decision-making is largely in the hands of the state.

But this is not the only way of interaction between the state and the organized interests of different groups of the population. Another way is that the state concludes with some of the pressure groups or interest groups a kind of convention (explicit or implicit agreement), receiving in exchange for certain privileges presented to it its loyalty and a guarantee of promoting state interests. If in the first case we can talk about lobbying as pressure on the state from interest groups, then in the second case we are talking about lobbying as an "exchange" or "contact".

In the first case, this is called a pluralistic type of representation of interests, in the second, it is a corporate type of representation.

Pluralism is a type of representation of interests when pressure groups are organized spontaneously, they are numerous, compete with each other and do not organize spontaneously, and, moreover, are not organized into some kind of hierarchical system. They themselves, completely independently of the state,

determine their interests, their leaders, and how independently of the state they determine their interests, their leaders, and how far they can go in pursuit of this interest. There may be several such groups in the same field of activity. None of them has a monopoly on representing interests. Achievement of any of them their goal, that is, influencing the state, is the result of competition.

The corporate type of representation of interests differs from the pluralistic root image. In this latter case, interest groups (at least those that have real opportunities to influence government policy) are relatively small, functionally ordered (that is, each of the groups is “responsible” for some special category of interests), hierarchical. The source of this order is the state. It is it that recognizes for this group the monopoly right to represent a certain interest in exchange for the right to influence in a certain way the determination of this interest, the selection of leaders, and so on.

It turns out that the main sign of pluralism is competition, the free competition of pressure groups in their influence on the state, while in corporatism there is a kind of “cartel agreement”, functional differentiation and the monopoly of certain groups to represent certain interests.

Thus, one can speak of a pluralistic lobby and a corporatist lobby. We are not going to define here which is worse and which is better. They rarely exist in their pure form, most often they are synthesized.

Let us try to find out what place Uzbek lobbyism occupies in the system of interaction between interest groups and the state, although it is still possible to talk about this system only conditionally, since the political and socio-economic factors that determine its main parameters have not finally come to light. As in most other countries, the main objects of lobbying influence in Uzbekistan are state bodies, endowed with power and administrative powers. By influencing the process of developing and adopting economic and socio-political decisions, lobbyists ensure a closer connection between society and the state and thereby make the latter capable of promptly responding to impulses emanating from influential public structures. On a broader, systemic level, lobbying activity is one of the most important forms of society’s influence on the state, ensuring their interaction along the functional line. Unlike territorial representation, carried out through political parties, elections and legislative bodies, functional representation is implemented directly. Its subjects do not need to prove their rights to access the authorities through elections or in any other way. The basis for such access is the social significance of a potential lobbyist, his real weight and influence in a particular sphere of social and political life.

Due to the fact that there are many interested groups and parties (our consideration: Artel, Akfa, UzAuto, Auto-test, “Texnopark”, “Dori-darmon” JSC, Akfa Medline, new universities and etc.) operating in Uzbekistan, its political

system has acquired a relatively holistic character, and here there are both main channels of interaction between society and the state. Representation on the party line is combined with representation on the line of interests. The first is of a general political nature and leads to the adoption of the most significant legislative acts, the second is specific and designed to ensure that the specific requests and needs of the forces, organizations and institutions operating in society are taken into account. However, what has been said does not mean at all that there is nothing in common between these representations and that each of them acts independently of one another. There is no such kind of independence even in countries with established democratic order. And this, in particular, prompts to consider lobbying in a broader context, including here the system of legislative power and the lawmaking process in general.

With regard to Uzbekistan, such a formulation of the issue is also dictated by considerations related to the special role of lobbyism in making government decisions, which was mentioned. At the same time, we mean not so much the mechanism of lobbying as those anomalies that follow from the very nature of the Uzbek political system and its institutions.

So, how to limit the possibilities of “wild” lobbying in conditions when the establishment of institutions of functional representation in Uzbekistan is just beginning? Over the past 10 years, a number of parliamentarians, public and scientific figures in foreign countries have actively sought the adoption of a law on lobbying. Similar acts are in force in the USA and Canada; in most Western European countries they do not exist, but lobbying practice is regulated there by a set of other laws regulating, for instance, the status of deputies, the work of elected authorities, the activities of voluntary associations, election campaigns, referendums. That is why we should also set particular norms about managing lobbying in particular normative legal acts such as, as we noted above, the status of deputies, the work of elected authorities, the activities of voluntary associations, election campaigns, etc.

There are also classifications of lobbyism and types of lobbyists. According to the regional grounds:

- Federal lobbyism;
- Regional lobbyism;
- Local lobbyism.

According to the spheres which lobbyism is going into:

- Industrial;
- Economical;
- Social;
- Educational;
- Medical.

According to the form its activity;

- Opened lobbyism;
- Closed lobbyism (also shadow lobbyism or black lobbyism, corridor lobbyism).

Types of lobbyists:

- Employee Lobbyist;
- Contract Lobbyist;
- Volunteer Lobbyist;
- Unsalariated Lobbyist;
- Self-Employed Lobbyist;
- Casual Lobbyist.

There is also need to identify the subjects of lobbying activities. There are various criteria and options for their classification. Some authors group them according to the principle of clans or clientele, formed around one goal or those or other influential figures.

Another variant of the classification of lobbying structures is the classification according to the institutional and functional characteristics. This approach, allowing to identify stable groups and associations, their composition and nature, at the same time makes it possible to establish the essence of the systemic connections that they have with government agencies. Revealing such connections, in turn, opens the way to clarifying the place and role of lobbyism in the political system and determining the nature of the evolution of itself, the entire system, and the structures of civil society, the most important elements of which are interest groups.

In accordance with this approach, four main groups of lobbyists are distinguished: politicized, social, economic, regional.

The first is the groupings of business and its political representatives, which seek political influence through participation in elections and are directly involved in the political struggle.

In Western society, entrepreneurs do not seek to directly represent their interests in the political arena, preferring to act through parties and movements close to them, or, conversely, use them directly on their own behalf (S. Berlusconi and his Forward, Italy!).

Attempts to establish social partnership at the macro level can also be viewed as an example of the intertwining of the interests of “politicized” and social lobbyists (in the absence of a clear distinction between lobbyist groups in general).

Protecting the interests of employees is the weakest link in tripartism. Trade unions do not have channels of independent political influence, and often they are “in the same boat” with entrepreneurs (this applies to both the micro

and macro levels), delegating to them representation of their interests before the legislative branch. The lobbying potential of trade unions is directly proportional to the economic importance of the industry or economic unit they represent: air traffic controllers, oil workers, miners, locomotive crew drivers have much more opportunities to lobby for their interests than social workers, science, and so on.

For a group of economic lobbyists, economic measures are the most effective levers of pressure on government decision-making. We include financial and industrial groups, corporations and industry complexes among these lobbyists. Financial and industrial groups - a form of self-organization of domestic capital - integrate banks with industry, trade, insurance and are gradually turning into the supporting structure of the emerging economic mechanism.

Limited resources and political instability make it inevitable that lobbying groups in a particular sector of the economy and society will fight for the right to monopolistically represent on behalf of a certain category of interests. In turn, the authorities, prompted by the need to overcome the crisis of statehood, will provide such a monopoly in exchange for political support. The most powerful pressure groups will turn into full-fledged partners of the government. It is possible that, once formed, such a structure can even receive legal, up to constitutional registration. Such a "state of monopolies" will become a reliable support for a moderate, authoritarian, but stable political regime.

Is a "good" scenario or "bad" is another matter. Of course, the activities of state and public organizations dealing with the problems of regulating the activities of pressure groups should be focused on the development of norms and conditions for the work of civilized pluralist lobbying. Such an organization of lobbying would be more in line with the broadly understood public interest.

More specifically, we need constant pressure from the public and legislators to create a legal basis for pluralist lobbying. First of all, a number of laws should be adopted to regulate and limit lobbying influence. These are the law on corruption, the law on civil service, laws governing the financing of electoral campaigns, the ownership and use of the media, and much more. Only on this basis is it possible to adopt a law on lobbying. I would especially like to note the key role in the "cultivation" of media lobbying. The point is to widely acquaint citizens in newspapers and magazines with the manifestations of this phenomenon.

In developed democracies, the emergence of civilized lobbying required decades or even centuries of development. We should use other people's experience and, relying on it, anticipate and direct the natural development of events.

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